

Yield and yield components in main and full plant ratoon crops. Faizabad, India, 1986.

Variety	Main						Ratoon crop					Total	
	Duration (d)	Tillers/plant	Effective tillers/plant	Grains/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Effective tillers/plant	Grains/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (d)	Yield (t/ha)
NDR119	94	18	16	86	16.5	3.0	33	15	81.0	16.2	2.4	127	5.4
NDR1001	90	17	16	88	16.0	3.2	36	14	83.0	15.8	2.7	126	5.8
NDR118	96	16	15	94	18.0	3.6	35	14	90.0	17.7	2.0	131	5.6
NDR102	95	17	14	92	17.5	3.7	34	16	89.0	17.2	2.1	129	5.8
NDR312	97	18	15	91	17.8	3.6	36	15	85.0	17.6	2.1	133	5.6
CD (0.05)						0.7					0.6		

crop by harvesting only panicles, leaving the leaves and stem intact. New shoots arose from higher nodes, instead of the ground tillers as in traditional ratooning. The number of branches emerging from each tiller and total tillers approached the number in the main crop, and in some plants even exceeded it.

Each branch developed 2-3 small

leaves. Panicle size almost matched that of the main crop. The ratoon crop matured in 34-36 d, with yield levels approaching 80-85% of the main crop (see table).

The experiment was conducted with very short-duration varieties. The nursery was sown on 19 Jun 1986, 25-d-old seedlings were transplanted at

1 seedling/hill in 12- × 5-m plots with 20- × 15-cm spacing and 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha. The ratoon crop was fertilized with 30-75 kg NP/ha.

Yields of the different varieties were similar. This technique costs more because of the need for hand sickle harvesting of the main crop without disturbing the shoot system. □

Effect of phosphates on flooded rice

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We evaluated superphosphate (SP), Mussoorie rock phosphate (MRP), and Mussoorie rock phosphate plus

Effect of P source and level on rice yield. Mangalore, India, 1984-86.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	1984-85	1985-86
<i>Main plot</i>		
Control	3.3	3.1
SP	3.9	3.5
MRP	3.3	3.1
MRP + SP (75 + 25)	3.5	3.2
MRP + SP (50 + 50)	3.6	3.2
MRP + SP (25 + 75)	3.8	3.4
DAP	3.9*	3.5*
F test		
SEm ±	0.12	0.06
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.2
<i>Subplot</i>		
0 kg P/ha	3.3	3.0
13.2 kg P/ha	3.6	3.3
26.4 kg P/ha	3.8	3.4
39.6 kg P/ha	3.8	3.3
F test	ns	0.01
SEm ±	0.14	0.04
CD (0.05)	ns	0.1
Interaction	ns	Significant

superphosphate (MRP + SP) and diammonium phosphate (DAP) in the midland soils of coastal Karnataka during the 1984 and 1985 wet seasons.

Soil was sandy clay loam, Ustoxtropept with pH 5.0, electrical conductivity 0.2 dS/m at 25 °C, 1.26% organic C, 56 kg P/ha, and 83 kg K/ha. Available micronutrients (in ppm) were Zn 0.25, Cu 1.86, Mn 0.38, Fe 57.7, and B 0.50. The experiment was in a split-plot design with P sources in main plots and P levels in subplots, including a no-P control.

Three 27-d-old IET2911 (medium duration) seedlings/hill were transplanted at 15- × 15-cm spacing. All plots received 100 kg N and 88 kg K/ha.

Half the N was applied at transplanting, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. P was applied at transplanting.

The field was flooded from transplanting to maturity and the crop protected from insects, diseases, and weeds.

Fertilizer sources gave significantly different yields in both years (see table). The higher yield with SP alone or DAP were comparable to that with MRP + SP (25% + 75%).

Yield with 26.4 kg P/ha was significantly higher than with other levels. The interaction effects were also significant in 1985-86. Locally available MRP is an inexpensive source of P. □

Effect of basally applied coated urea on grain yield

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In Cauvery Delta, farmers usually apply N as urea in split doses. But with monsoon weather, water stagnation in the field, and social factors, N often is not applied on time.

We compared N applied in a single basal dose as coal-tar-coated urea (CCU), neem-coated urea (NCU), sulfur-coated urea (SCU), and urea supergranules (USG), to N applied in 3 splits (50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation) as prilled urea (PU).

Two experiments were conducted Jun-Sep 1983 and 1984 using short-duration rice varieties (110-115 d) in a randomized block design with four

replications. Soil was clay loam, with low available N, medium available P and K, and pH 7.5.

Basal CCU (1%) and NCU (5%)

yields were not significantly different from that with PU in splits.

Yields with SCU broadcast and USG deep point placed 2 d after transplanting

were not significantly different from that with split applications of PU.

Split-applied urea was the least expensive practice. □

Applying nitrogen with sesbania

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Yields with and without sesbania green manure and three levels of N as urea in different splits were studied in a field experiment laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications during 1986 kharif. Soil was a sandy loam (Typic Ustochrept) with pH 8.2, EC 0.15 dS/m, organic C 0.34%, total N 0.06% Olsen's P 10 kg/ha, and a percolation rate of 5 mm/h.

Sesbania grown in situ for 7 wk was incorporated 1 d before transplanting. Sesbania dry matter was 24 t/ha, with

Sesbania plus N effects on yield. Ludhiana, India, 1986 kharif.

Treatment	N application (kg/ha) at indicated time			Grain yield (t/ha)
	0 DT	21 DT	42 DT	
No sesbania + no N	—	—	—	4.8
No sesbania + 120 kg N/ha	40	40	40	7.4
No sesbania + 180 kg N/ha	60	60	60	8.2
Sesbania + no N	—	—	—	7.0
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	60	—	—	8.1
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	—	60	—	7.8
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	30	—	30	8.1
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	30	30	—	7.7
Sesbania + 60 kg N/ha	—	30	30	8.4
Sesbania + 120 kg N/ha	—	60	60	8.4
Sesbania + 120 kg N/ha	40	40	40	9.0
LSD (P = 0.05)				0.4

106 kg N/ha. All plots received 26 kg P and 23 kg K/ha at the final puddling. Sesbania green manure plus 60 kg N/ha yielded more than sesbania with 120 kg N/ha (see table). Applying 60 kg N/ha

in 2 equal splits at 21 d and 42 d after transplanting (DT) was most efficient.

If 120 kg N/ha is applied with green manure, 3 equal splits at 0, 21, and 42 DT gave the highest yield. □

Responses of rice to N, P, and Zn in semireclaimed alkali soil

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P deficiency has been a major cause of low yields in semireclaimed alkali soils. We studied the effect of P fertilization with N and Zn in a semireclaimed alkali

Effect of P application with N and Zn on yield in a semireclaimed alkali soil. Karnal, India.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Zero	17.5 kg P	Mean
N 120 Z 0	4.9	5.2	5.0
N 160 Z 0	5.2	5.3	5.2
N 80 Z 20	4.5	5.0	4.8
N 120 Z 20	5.4	6.6	6.0
N 160 Z 20	5.8	7.5	6.6
N 200 Z 20	5.7	7.1	6.4
Mean	5.2	6.1	
LSD (0.05)			
N		0.72	
P		0.36	
N × P		ns	

soil. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with four replications.

Half the N and all the P and Zn were applied at transplanting as urea, single superphosphate, and zinc sulfate. The remaining N was topdressed in 2 equal splits at 3 and 6 wk after transplanting. Recommended agronomic practices were followed.

Originally the soil had been highly sodic (pH 10.45), but gypsum application and 4 yr cropping had reduced pH to 8.8, EC to 0.42 dS/m,

and exchangeable sodium percentage to 19 in 0-15 cm surface soil. The soil had loamy texture, 0.28% organic C, 2.73% CaCO₃, 0.5 mg DTPA-Zn/kg, 76 mg available N, 3.96 mg available P, and 140 mg available K/kg.

Applying N and Zn without P had no effect on yield. Applying N, P, and Zn together significantly increased yield (see table). A balanced application of 160 kg N, 17.5 kg P, and 4.5 kg Zn/ha gave the maximum yield. □

Effects of several urea-based N sources

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We compared 6 urea sources — prilled urea (PU), urea supergranule (USG), large granule urea (LGU), neem cake-coated urea (NCU), rock phosphate-

coated urea (RPU), and sulfur-coated urea (SCU) — at 37.5, 112.5, and 150 kg N/ha in a 1986 dry season field experiment. Soil was a fine loamy hyperthermic Typic Haplaquept with pH 5.3, organic C 0.46%, CEC 4.3 meq/100 g, 215 kg available N/ha (alk. permanganate method), 6.5 kg available P/ha (NaHCO₃ extract), and 37 kg available K/ha (ammonium acetate extract). The experiment was in a split-